

1 Risk management plans to overcome barriers for safe reuse of 2 urban wastewater for agricultural purposes in Europe.

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7 Abstract

8 Despite their multiple benefits, water-reuse practices are scarcely implemented globally
9 owing to factors hindering the reuse process and socio-political issues that are closely
10 related to the lack of trust in water-reuse techniques and practices. Non-homogeneity
11 in the water-reuse regulations is also highly relevant. To overcome these challenges, the
12 European Parliament has recently approved the Regulation 2020/741 *on minimum
13 requirements for water reuse*, to standardise the legal requirements of wastewater to
14 be considered fit for reuse. This regulation also requires elaboration of Water Reuse Risk
15 Management Plans (WRRMPs) for all reclamation facilities of the Union. This review
16 aims to provide a general overview of the current limitations and gaps in developing
17 water-reuse practices, as well as recommendations that could overcome them. To this
18 end, WRRMPs play a crucial role because they can ensure the healthy and safe use of
19 reclaimed water in agriculture. Consequently, they can serve as tools to change the
20 public perception of wastewater, from a waste to a source of water. Previous guidelines
21 to develop risk management plans and the current regulations regarding water reuse in
22 Europe have also been extensively analysed in this study.

23

24 Keywords

25 Irrigation; risk assessment; risk management; wastewater; water reuse.

26

27 1. Introduction

28 Water scarcity is one of the greatest challenges worldwide, because approximately 40%
29 of the global land area is classified as arid, semi-arid, or dry sub-humid, and over two
30 billion people experience high water stress [1,2]. The situation is deteriorating because
31 of climate change and increasing population. The agricultural sector has the largest
32 water use, accounting for approximately 70% of the total extracted water [3]. Therefore,
33 alternative water sources must be explored to ensure adequate water supply. In this
34 context, appropriately treated municipal wastewater (termed as reclaimed water) can
35 help to compensate for the gap between available and required water worldwide,
36 providing a regular water supply [4]. Wastewater reuse in agriculture involves numerous
37 environmental and social benefits, both monetary and non-monetary. It reduces the
38 exploitation of natural water resources, decreases pressure on their water basins,
39 improves the ecological status of water bodies, alleviates poverty in water-scarce
40 developing countries, and ensures socio-economic and political stability [5–7].

41 Approximately 312,000 hm³ of municipal wastewater is estimated to be produced
42 worldwide annually [8]. Conventional municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs)
43 have been designed with the aim to reduce the concentration of some pollutants
44 (mainly organic matter, suspended solids and nutrients) below limits established in the

45 legislation. Hence, they follow a linear approach where resources contained in the
 46 wastewater are not utilised (Figure 1). However, WWTPs can be substituted by (or
 47 transformed into) reclamation facilities to maximise the production of reclaimed water,
 48 combined with energy and nutrient recovery, and transition towards a circular economy
 49 [8,9]. Despite its substantial potential benefits, the percentage of wastewater reused
 50 (instead of only treated and discharged) remains low, except for certain cases, such as
 51 in Cyprus (Table 1).
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Figure 1. Representation of conventional (linear) and modern (circular) approaches used in municipal wastewater treatment systems.

Table 1. Worldwide data related to the production, collection, treatment and reuse of wastewater for agricultural purposes [10].

Area	Country	Produced municipal wastewater (hm ³ ·y ⁻¹)	Collected wastewater (%)	Treated wastewater (%)	Reuse of Treated Wastewater (hm ³ ·y ⁻¹)	Reused wastewater (%)	Reused wastewater in agriculture (%)	Water withdrawal for irrigation (hm ³ ·y ⁻¹)
Asia	China	48,510	64.2	100	7,720	15.7	16.3	385,200 ^a
	Japan	16,930	71.00	68.3	390	3.4	3.0	53,300
Africa	Egypt	7,078	91.8	60.5	2,400	56.0	12.1	45,110
	Tunisia	312	88.8	87.8	42	15.5	33.0	1,552
	South Africa	2,420	100	90.9	3,220	-	-	11,397
Central -Eastern Europe	Ukraine	1,513	-	59.1	6	0.7	-	4,052
	Romania	1,011	96.34	88.2	-	-	-	0,441
	Russian Federation	12,320	71.43	74.7	-	-	-	7,000
	Croatia	336	100	83.7	-	-	-	30
	Poland	2,168	96.36	61.3	6	0.5	-	84
Southern Europe	Cyprus	35	100	96.5	34	99.7	50.0	174
	Italy	3,926	-	99.4	90	2.3	96.7	16,000
	Malta	26	100	92.3	1	5.8	50.0	24
	Portugal	577	100	46.8	6	2.2	-	3,395
	Spain	5,206	100	90.0	1,184	25.3	-	18,645
Northern Europe	Denmark	368	100	100	-	-	-	51
Western Europe	France	4,000	94.25	94.25	822	21.8	-	2,588
	Germany	5,213 ^b	100.0	99.42	-	-	-	0,363
	UK	4,089	99.0	99.0	328	8.1	-	84
Middle East	Iran	3,548	32.8	24.9	328	37.1	-	86,000 ^a
	Israel	0,500	100	90.0	1,028	-	-	1,173 ^a
	Saudi Arabia	1,546	74.0	100	508	31.8	100	19,000 ^a

Northern America	Mexico	7,960	84.5	54.9	1,796	41.1	76.8	65,870
	Canada	6,074	97.3	95.5	-	-	-	2,950
	USA	60,410	78.2	75.1	5,548	12.2	-	163,000
Southern America	Argentina	2,458	64.9	11.8	182	62.8	-	27,930 ^a
	Brazil	10,081	65.7	51.9	100	1.8	8.0	32,160
	Colombia	2,397	100	6.4	-	-	-	16,000
Oceania	Australia	2,094	87.3	95.5	280	14.0	50.0	11,099

57 ^aReferred to annual quantity of self-supplied water withdrawn not only for irrigation, but also for livestock and aquaculture purposes.

58 ^bAmount of wastewater collected.

59 The limited use of reclaimed water is related to the risks associated with the pollutants
60 contained in wastewater effluents, especially in developing countries, where
61 wastewater is partially treated or untreated [3,5]. In addition, numerous end-users and
62 the general public commonly consider wastewater as waste rather than a source for
63 reclaiming water. Thus, to shift this paradigm, ensuring safety of the environment and
64 public health in the use of reclaimed water is essential. These are the main goals of the
65 Water Reuse Risk Management Plans (WRRMPs), which are mandatory for all reclaimed
66 water facilities implemented in the European Union (EU) after applying the Regulation
67 2020/741 *on minimum requirements for water reuse* (discussed in detail in Section 4.2).
68 This review aims to analyse the factors that currently hinder water-reuse practices and
69 discuss the role of risk management in its implementation. To this end, this paper is
70 divided into the following sections: Section 1 is the introduction of the topic; Section 2
71 evaluates, from a European perspective, the main techno-economic and socio-political
72 barriers that hinder the widespread use of reclaimed water; Section 3 analyses the role
73 of risk assessment in water reuse, including the most relevant guidelines for risk
74 assessment; Section 4 provides a critical discussion regarding the current national and
75 European legislation, presenting some of their major gaps; and Section 5 proposes
76 methodologies, tools, and practices (alternative and complementary to WRRMPs) that
77 can help overcome the determined barriers to the implementation of water-reuse
78 practices.

79

80 2. Barriers to the widespread application of wastewater-reuse 81 practices

82 The development of wastewater reuse has diverse challenges, including those related
83 to the water reclamation process itself, that is, process feasibility and the presence of
84 potentially damaging microorganisms and compounds in the reclaimed water, as well as
85 socio-political barriers, which are further described in Section 2.2.

86

87 2.1. Barriers related to the water-reuse process

88 Reclaimed water presents intrinsic risks associated with the presence of biological and
89 chemical pollutants in wastewater, because they can have negative impacts on public
90 health and the environment. These risks cannot be eliminated completely but can be
91 minimised to safe levels. Although current WWTPs are highly efficient in removing
92 certain pollutants (organic matter, solids, nutrients), evidence on the mechanism by
93 which they effectively deal with other pollutants such as metals, contaminants of
94 emerging concern (CECs), and some biological pollutants (pathogenic microorganisms,
95 antibiotic resistance bacteria, etc.) remain limited [11,12]. The extent of the risks
96 associated with the CECs depends on the degree of wastewater treatment (secondary,
97 tertiary or quaternary), type of pollutant, and especially, on pollutant influent
98 concentrations. Poorly treated industrial wastewater and/or runoff water in municipal
99 wastewater streams can add significant amounts of pollutants, increasing the risks
100 associated with its reuse [4]. Thus, pollutant reduction is crucial for improving the safe
101 reuse of wastewater, especially from the source of production.

102 The presence of pathogens (such as bacteria, viruses, protozoa and others) in
103 wastewater effluent streams is extremely common, as many WWTPs lack appropriate
104 biomass-water separation systems and/or tertiary treatments. Pathogens cause human
105 diseases, that can be both chronic and acute, and even premature mortality, thus they
106 are of high health concern [5]. Consequently, referent pathogenic organisms are
107 included in the risk assessment guidelines (described in Section 3) and legislation and
108 regulations related to water reuse (discussed in Section 4).

109 The presence of heavy metals in wastewater is also common. They can accumulate in
110 soils and the food chain, negatively affecting crop productivity [13,14]. Therefore, the
111 risks associated with the presence of metals in reclaimed water must be assessed and
112 minimised. Concerns are also increasing regarding the presence in water of CECs such
113 as pharmaceuticals, antibiotics, pesticides, microplastics, and antidepressants. The risk
114 assessment of CECs presents several challenges: i) detection and analyses of CECs are
115 not always accurate because they are diverse and commonly present at trace levels [15],
116 ii) monitoring and analysis of CECs are complex and expensive due to the requirement
117 of specialised equipment and the excessively high number of compounds to be analysed
118 [16,17], iii) they can affect human health and the environment (including flora and
119 fauna) at trace levels [12,18], iv) they are usually highly resistant to biological removal
120 in WWTPs [12], v) degradation compounds can present higher toxicity than the original
121 CECs [4], and vi) CECs can persist and accumulate in crop lands and the food chain [19].
122 To effectively assess the risks associated with CECs, guidelines that provide target
123 compounds, detection techniques, and safe CEC concentration limits must be developed
124 by experts, but they are currently limited.

125 Among all groups of CECs, antibiotics require special attention, not only because of their
126 increasing presence in urban wastewater streams and the potential toxic effects of
127 antibiotics entering the human food chain [20], but also because they contribute to the
128 development of antibiotic resistance genes (ARG) and antibiotic-resistant bacteria (ARB)
129 [11,16]. This has become a topic of major concern for the scientific community [21],
130 because the increasing spread of ARGs threatens modern medicine and lifestyles,
131 especially in developed countries, which are highly antibiotic-dependent. However,
132 knowledge related to long-term risks due to the presence of ARG or ARB in reclaimed
133 water remains scarce [11,22], and most of these compounds are commonly stated as
134 potential risks.

135 Some techno-economic hurdles, which typically vary for developed and developing
136 countries, also affect the implementation of water reclamation facilities. In developing
137 countries, wastewater collection is not always effective and wastewater treatment
138 systems are scarce or inefficient, hindering appropriate wastewater management [5].
139 However, in developed countries, additional infrastructure is often required for the
140 transition from conventional WWTPs to reclamation facilities. These infrastructures are
141 primarily related to i) tertiary treatment for the disinfection, nutrient and salinity
142 removal, or any other additional processes beyond traditional treatment; ii) storage
143 infrastructures to align the production and demand of reclaimed water; iii) piping
144 systems for the distribution of reclaimed water from the facilities to crop lands; and iv)
145 adequate number of instructed personnel to operate and manage the reclamation
146 facilities. These imply additional costs and difficulties that sometimes disincentivise the
147 use of reclaimed water for irrigation [23]. For instance, based on the tertiary treatment
148 technologies selected (ultraviolet, ozone, membrane filtration, etc.), operating costs can

149 increase by approximately 0.02–0.21 €·m⁻³ [24,25]. For comparison, the cost of
150 extracting water from rivers and groundwater bodies is estimated to be only 0.015–0.2
151 €·m⁻³ [26].

152

153 [2.2. Barriers related to socio-political aspects](#)

154 Other obstacles in the use of reclaimed water are related to the engagement of policy-
155 makers and stakeholders, the high number and variety of public organisations involved
156 in decisions related to water management, and inadequate understanding of some roles
157 and responsibilities that can lead to conflicts and ineffective management strategies
158 [23]. Although collaboration between these actors is intended, it is not always successful
159 in practice. Owing to these political issues, a lack of homogeneity in regional and
160 national regulations regarding water reclamation has been observed (refer to Section
161 4.1 for details), which is one of the main obstacles to the widespread development of
162 water reuse in Europe [27]. Differences in regulations include the type and number of
163 monitored pollutants, as well as their limiting values, which can be even as stringent as
164 those for drinking water in certain regulations [28]. This lack of homogeneity hinders
165 transport and supply of agricultural products irrigated with reclaimed water [23]. The
166 EU is increasingly making efforts to align policies and government decisions in the water
167 sector, supporting the development of guidelines and policies to help boost water reuse.
168 The European Parliament (2020) has recently launched *Regulation 2020/741 on*
169 *minimum requirements for water reuse* (to be applied in all member states from 26 June
170 2023) to standardise water-reuse regulations in the Union and overcome challenges
171 hindering their implementation (more information in Section 4.2).

172 Social factors, such as religious beliefs or negative opinions regarding the use of
173 reclaimed water, are also worth considering because they can threaten the technical,
174 economic, political, and legal advances that can be made in the sector [29]. For instance,
175 in a case study analysed in Tunisia, political and economic efforts were made to reduce
176 the costs of acquiring reclaimed water to 0.018 €·m⁻³, which implied lower price than
177 surface water (0.026–0.092 €·m⁻³). However, the farmers were reluctant to shift the
178 paradigm and preferred to use conventional water [30]. A significant proportion of the
179 general public does not trust water-reuse regulations, monitoring practices and the
180 managing organisations, the technical process, and the quality and safety of the
181 reclaimed water itself [31,32]. Hence, increasing the awareness regarding the benefits
182 of water reuse, combined with improving transparency and ensuring the safety and low
183 impacts of water reuse, are essential to expand this practice worldwide. Risk assessment
184 and management plans (mandatory in Europe after the approval of Regulation 2020/741
185 on 26 June 2023) are clearly aligned with the abovementioned aims. By ensuring safe
186 water reuse, the reputation and perception of reclaimed water facilities can be
187 maintained at high levels [33]. Thus, WRRMPs seem to be useful tools for boosting water
188 reuse in agriculture [18].

189

190 3. Risk assessment in water reuse

191 Risk assessment is the key step of management and implementation plans for water
192 reuse and consists of the identifying and characterising possible hazardous events to
193 evaluate related risks and prioritise them [34]. This requires the definition of hazards,
194 hazardous events, and risks associated with the water-reuse process. Hazards refer to

195 any agent that could harm people or ecosystems and can be divided into biological,
196 chemical, physical, or radiological. Accordingly, hazardous events occur when targets
197 (people and/or the environment) are exposed to hazards such as incidents, failures, or
198 situations which introduce, release, or amplify the presence of a hazard in the system
199 [35]. The likelihood of a hazard causing harm within a specified timeframe, including the
200 severity of the consequences, represents the risk.

201 The risks associated with reclaimed water differ according to the reuse purpose and
202 entail both risks for human health and for the environment. Health risks are partially
203 addressed by the existing legislation regarding the safety of agricultural products [36].
204 However, this legislation does not specify the requirements for reclaimed water used to
205 irrigate agricultural products, which can have other impacts on human health owing to
206 the direct exposure of farmers and surrounding residents to the pollutants contained in
207 water [37]. Environmental risks owing to the presence of chemical contaminants,
208 inorganic salts, nutrients, and heavy metals in water must also be considered. In general,
209 such risks should be carefully analysed prior to utilising wastewater as a water source
210 through a risk-based approach. In summary, risks associated with water reuse in
211 irrigation can be divided into three categories: i) health risks associated with consumers
212 of agricultural products irrigated with reclaimed water, including those related to the
213 health of animals that consume crops irrigated with reclaimed water; ii) health risks
214 associated with humans exposed to reclaimed water (workers, bystanders, and
215 residents in nearby communities); and iii) risks to the local environment, that is, surface
216 waters, groundwater, soil, and ecosystems [5,14,38].

217

218 3.1. Existing guidelines and methodologies for risk management plans in the
219 water-reuse sector

220 Minimising the health and environmental risks associated with water reuse is a complex
221 task that requires a comprehensive knowledge of the process. Owing to the lack of
222 specific regulations and standard procedures for risk management, the main
223 international organisations involved in public health and environmental protection have
224 provided guidelines and manuals to address risk management for water-reuse projects.
225 However, this is approached from different perspectives based on the specific case at a
226 specific time. Some organisations [34,39] aimed to provide technical indications for the
227 design of reclaimed facility projects. In contrast, the Australian Government Initiative
228 [40], Sanitation Safety Planning (SSP) [35], and DEMOWARE [41] guidelines have
229 presented content to develop risk management plans to consistently ensure the safety
230 and acceptability of water reclamation.

231 Owing to their relevance in the water-reuse sector recently, the following guidelines and
232 manuals are evaluated. i) Guidelines for municipal water reuse in the Mediterranean
233 region [42]; ii) Guidelines for the safe use of wastewater, excreta, and greywater,
234 Volume II- Wastewater use in agriculture [34]; iii) Australian Guidelines for Water
235 Recycling: Managing Health and Environmental Risks [40]; iv) Guidelines for Water
236 Reuse [39]; v) ISO 16075 Guidelines for Treated Wastewater Use for Irrigation Projects
237 [43]; vi) SSP – manual for safe use and disposal of wastewater, greywater, and excreta
238 [35]; vii) Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment [44]; and viii) Water Reuse Safety Plans
239 (WRSPs)- a manual for practitioners by DEMOWARE [41] (Table 2).

240

241

Table 2: Summary of the information provided by guidelines for water reuse and safety plans.

	UNEP [42]	WHO Guidelines [34]	Australian Guidelines [40]	EPA [39]	ISO 16075:2020 [43]	ISO 20426:2018 [45]	SSP [35]	QMRA [44]	DEMOWARE [41]
Water reuse practices	- Urban and agricultural reuse. - 4 quality classes.	Agricultural reuse of wastewater, greywater and excreta	- Urban reuse. - Irrigation in agriculture. - Industrial reuse	- Urban. - Industrial. - Agricultural. - Impoundment. - Environmental. - Groundwater recharge. - Potable reuse.	Agricultural and urban irrigation projects;	Non-potable reuse: agricultural, urban, industrial, recreational and environmental	Agricultural reuse of wastewater, greywater and excreta	Water Safety Management. all uses.	All possible reuses
Water quality criteria	- Intestinal nematodes. - E.coli. - Faecal coliforms. - Suspended solids.	- Reference pathogens: Campylobacter, Cryptosporidium, Rotavirus. - Risks expressed in DALYs.	Reference pathogens, soil and plant toxic compounds. Risk expressed in DALYs.	Faecal coliforms, BOD, Turbidity, pH, residual Cl ₂ , metals and soil characteristics	BOD, TSS, Turbidity, thermotolerant coliforms, intestinal nematodes, organic matter, nutrients salts and heavy metals	<i>E.coli</i> , BOD, TSS or Turbidity Chlorine residual	Reference pathogens (e.g., Campylobacter, Cryptosporidium, Rotavirus). Risk expressed in DALYs.	Reference pathogens (e.g., Campylobacter, Cryptosporidium, Rotavirus). Risk expressed in DALYs.	Microbial, toxic, Compounds of agronomic relevance, and Compounds of emerging concern (no limits)
Risks addressed	Microbial	- Health risks (priority) - Environmental	Health and environmental	Health and environmental	Health and environmental	Health	Health	Microbial	Health risks (priority) - Environmental aspects
Risk assessment	No. Reuse based on limit values.	Microbial analysis, Epidemiological study, QMRA	Qualitative and Quantitative risk assessment	No. Reuse based on limit values. Methods for assessment specified in other documents (https://www.epa.gov/risk/conducting-human-health-risk-assessment#tab-5)	- No. Reuse based on limit values	Qualitative and Quantitative health risk assessment	Qualitative and Quantitative risk assessment.	Quantitative risk assessment	Qualitative and Quantitative risk assessment

Risk management	Multi-barrier approach	Multi-barrier approach	Multi-barrier approach	Multi-barrier approach	Multi-barrier approach	Multi-barrier approach	Multi-barrier approach	Multi-barrier approach	Multi-barrier approach
Monitoring	Minimum frequencies and sampling points	Validation, Operational, Verification	Validation, Operational, Verification at critical control points	Frequencies depending on intended use.	Operational monitoring on wastewater, crops, soil and environment in ISO 16075	Parameters to be monitored and log removals	Validation, Operational, Verification	-	Operational
Social aspects	No contemplated	- Public perception. - Economic feasibility. - Policy aspects	- Acceptance. - Communication strategies.	- Public Outreach. - Participation, and Consultation.	No contemplated	No contemplated	Supporting programs	No contemplated	- Acceptance. - Communication.
Advantages	Specific for the most common practices in the Mediterranean region.	Referenced data, e.g., epidemiologic studies, concentrations in wastewater, crops and soil, log removals.	Complete of referenced characterisations, limits, examples and recommendations for risk management	- Referenced data - Provide suggestions from the planning and management phase to the public participation and consultation phase. - Address the existing regulatory framework to minimise the related risk - Discuss the funding possibilities available for water reuse projects.	Provide design and technical specifications for treatment, storage, distribution and irrigation infrastructure.	Provide guidelines to evaluate qualitative and quantitative risk assessment	Provide examples	Address the core phase of Risk assessment in a quantitative approach	Simplify the structure of a water reuse safety plan
Disadvantages	- Not addressed all possible reuses. - Not addressed environmental risks.	Focused mainly on developing countries.	- Complex. - Lot of data required	- Focused on US applications.	No social aspects included. No guidelines on risk assessment.	No social aspects included. No limit values specified	- Focused on developing countries.	Do not consider non-technical aspects, monitoring and implementation	- Non quantitative indications.

243 *DALYs: Disability-adjusted life years; EPA: United States Environmental Protection Agency; SSP: Sanitation Safety Planning; UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme;*
244 *WHO: World Health Organisation.*

245 3.1.1. *Water-reuse practices and quality criteria*

246 All guidelines analysed in this paper consider wastewater reuse for irrigation, although
247 some [39–41] include numerous possible uses, from aquifer recharge to urban,
248 industrial, and potable water reuse (Table 2). The selected wastewater reuse practice
249 also depends on the region in which the guidelines are focused on. For instance, the
250 WHO guidelines [34,35] are primarily formulated for developing countries where water
251 is reused for different purposes, such as agriculture and indirect potable reuse, based
252 on their needs. This is also considered in the EPA guidelines [39]. In contrast, the UNEP
253 guidelines [42] are specifically devised for the Mediterranean area, thus focusing on
254 agricultural reuse, while potable reuse is uncommon [28]. Water-use categories are also
255 defined based on comparable levels of risk, from urban reuse to unrestricted, restricted
256 irrigation, and irrigation using only efficient irrigation systems. The WRSP manual
257 proposed by Hochstrat et al. [41] aims to expand water applications to any type of reuse
258 and can enable operators and authorities to develop feasible management and safety
259 concepts for existing water-reuse systems.

260 For each intended use, almost all the guidelines provide quality standards to ensure
261 human health and environmental protection. Most of the water quality criteria consist
262 of threshold concentrations for reference biological pollutants, such as *Escherichia coli*,
263 *Campylobacter*, *Cryptosporidium*, Rotavirus, nematode eggs, and faecal coliforms (Table
264 2). Moreover, biological oxygen demand (BOD), turbidity, pH, and residual Cl₂ are
265 considered in the EPA [39], whereas the WHO [34], Australian, [40] and EPA [39]
266 guidelines also provide maximum concentrations of chemical pollutants and heavy
267 metals. Furthermore, the maximum concentrations in soil are only considered in the
268 WHO [34] and EPA [39] guidelines.

269

270 *3.1.2. Risk assessment in existing methodologies, management, and monitoring*
271 *techniques*

272 The assessment of potential risks for health and the environment could be summarised
273 by identifying hazards and hazardous events, estimating their likelihood, evaluating their
274 impacts, and characterising the corresponding risks [40]. The level of detail and
275 methodology used to assess risks may vary according to the specific needs and data
276 available. Some guidelines, such as the UNEP [42], do not specify a methodology for risk
277 assessment, limiting the provision of maximum values and barriers to ensure safe water
278 reuse. In contrast, most existing guidelines suggest sophisticated microbial analyses,
279 epidemiological studies, and QMRA and/or chemical risk assessment (QCRA)
280 approaches to be used when data and resources are available [46].

281 Health protection is the focus of risk assessment, although some guidelines also consider
282 environmental risk (Table 2). Both public health and the environment can be protected
283 by reducing or eliminating physical, biological and chemical pollutants in reclaimed
284 water. Limiting public exposure to reclaimed water by implementing multiple barriers,
285 such as retention time in storage systems, selected irrigation systems, setback distances
286 from the application site, entry restrictions, avoiding or preventing cross-connections
287 with potable water distribution systems or backflow prevention, and encoded
288 distribution systems, can minimise the direct contact of potentially contaminated water,
289 especially for population with higher risk of exposure, such as farmers, crop merchants,
290 agricultural product consumers, and residents from surrounding communities [5].
291 Particular attention is paid to the microbial risks caused by pathogens, providing specific
292 information for the calculation of microbial health-based performance targets. The

293 WHO [34,44] and Australian guidelines [40] consider 10^{-6} disability-adjusted life years
294 (DALYs) as the health limit, which corresponds to one infection per one million people
295 per year [39], whereas protection measures are evaluated considering the pathogen
296 reduction required to achieve this limit for different exposures [47]. In particular, QMRA
297 guidelines [44] provide information, data, and formulae to evaluate microbial risk and
298 compare them with the target DALYs. Health risks due to chemicals can be assessed
299 quantitatively through the QCRA by comparing estimated exposures to tolerable (or
300 acceptable) effect levels or concentrations [41]. Therefore, risk quotients (RQ), which
301 represent the ratio between the concentration at the endpoint and the respective
302 tolerable concentration or dose, can be calculated for each endpoint. An $RQ > 1$ indicates
303 that based on the current knowledge, risk is above the acceptable levels and reduction
304 measures should be implemented. However, an $RQ < 0.1$ is often defined as areas of
305 negligible risk [48]. Other targets must be defined for environmental risks. However,
306 limits or specific thresholds to minimise them are barely indicated in these guidelines,
307 which commonly delegate these aspects to current environmental regulations. Some
308 exceptions exist, such as the Australian guidelines [40] and EPA [39], which include risks
309 associated with chemicals that may cause plant toxicity (boron, chloride, sodium,
310 cadmium, and chlorine), soil degradation (salinity and sodium), or nutrient imbalance.
311 Excess water is also considered. The Australian guidelines [40] also provide particular
312 focus on CECs, which is a novel approach compared to the other guidelines (Table 2).
313 Among all evaluated guidelines, risk management was addressed using a multiple
314 barrier approach (Table 2). In general, control measures can be applied to target water
315 quality and/or to work on route exposure, including treatment (e.g. disinfection),
316 technical (e.g. drip irrigation), and behavioural measures (e.g. harvesting practices). The

317 WHO [34], Australian [40], and EPA [39] guidelines provide various treatment options to
318 meet specific water quality goals, based on the intended use. The treatment processes
319 are then combined with on-site controls, and restrictions are used to further reduce
320 risks.

321 Apart from the aforementioned factors, monitoring is crucial to ensure that the water-
322 reuse scheme effectively achieves defined performance and water quality targets. Thus,
323 it is a factor considered in all the analysed guidelines. Nonetheless, they differed in
324 various aspects, including the points of monitoring (treatment plant effluent, storage,
325 and point of use) and sampling frequency (Table 2). The WHO guidelines [34] introduced
326 three types of monitoring, depending on the operating step: i) validation monitoring
327 before the complete operational activity, ii) operational monitoring to ensure the
328 effectiveness of the control measures applied, and iii) verification monitoring to ensure
329 compliance with regulation at the end-use stage. Based on a similar approach, four types
330 of monitoring are used according to the Australian guidelines [40]: i) obtaining baseline
331 data, ii) validating the system, iii) obtaining operational data, and iv) verifying process
332 effectiveness. These sampling and monitoring campaigns should be conducted (at least)
333 at the critical control points, which represent essential points where risks are
334 significantly reduced or prevented, to appropriately evaluate the efficiency and efficacy
335 of barriers and preventive measures. The EPA guidelines [39] also include monitoring
336 programs for each intended use based on online methods and warning alarms. The
337 DEMOWARE manual [41] improves upon previous guidelines by including audits and
338 visual inspections using checklists and interviews to help operators better understand
339 the system's functionality and the background of the risk management process.

340

341 *3.1.3. Social aspects*

342 Consideration of public perception, social acceptability, and communication strategies
343 regarding wastewater reuse has increased recently (discussed further in Section 5.1);
344 therefore, these aspects have been considered in most of the cited guidelines (Table 2).
345 Community and stakeholder participation is often encouraged through educational and
346 information activities, public meetings, public consultations, and workshops. In the
347 Australian guidelines [40], particular attention is paid to public information and the
348 development of communication strategies, because communication modes and
349 phrasing can be highly relevant to increasing water-reuse practices [49]. Key messages,
350 as well as the main tools for communication and stakeholder engagement, are
351 suggested. The EPA guidelines [39] also include best management practices involving
352 community engagement, summarise water use in the United States, discuss the
353 expansion of water reuse nationally to meet water needs, and provide an overview of
354 numerous national and international water-reuse case studies. In addition to the
355 aforementioned strategies, the DEMOWARE manual [41] states that the acceptance of
356 water-reuse projects is more challenging than implementing water supply infrastructure
357 because water-reuse practices are generally perceived critically.

358

359 *3.1.4. General advantages and disadvantages*

360 All the analysed guidelines have contributed to developing safe water-reuse applications
361 and have provided instructions guiding operators in the design and realisation of water-
362 reuse projects, as well as politicians and decision-makers responsible for establishing
363 regulations to assess and standardise those practices.

364 In particular, the UNEP guidelines [42] overcame the lack of existing regulations in the
365 Mediterranean region at that time, whereas the WHO guidelines [34] were particularly
366 helpful in determining referenced and quantitative information regarding the presence
367 of pathogens, removal efficiencies, and proposed thresholds, as they provided summary
368 tables and supporting material. However, these guidelines mostly focused on
369 developing countries, and only general information about water-reuse management
370 plans was provided. The SSP Manual [35] improved upon the WHO guidelines [34] by
371 providing a systematic approach in six modules to assess, manage, and monitor risks
372 from wastewater origin to its final use, including examples and case studies that are
373 especially useful for developing countries. The QMRA guidelines [44] provide useful
374 information on evaluating and quantifying microbial risks, even if they are not designed
375 to cover the implementation of a management plan such as monitoring programs or
376 communication.

377 The Australian guidelines [40] can be considered pioneers because they developed a
378 complete risk management plan and established the basis for future regulations,
379 including the European 2020/741 (further discussed in Section 4.2). However, the EPA
380 guidelines [39] offer more detailed information about a wide range of reuse applications
381 and introduce new concepts as well as treatment technologies that support water-reuse
382 operations. Moreover, these guidelines emphasise the need for further investigation of
383 CECs before establishing their threshold limits. However, methodologies that address
384 the risks of CECs have not yet been specified; thus, considering them is extremely
385 challenging because of the difficulties in their monitoring (refer to Section 2.1 for
386 details). The DEMOWARE manual [41] provides a simpler (compared to its predecessors)
387 methodological guideline for the development of WRSPs to support operators and

388 authorities in designing and developing water-reuse schemes. Some examples of case
389 studies are also presented, although they do not provide specific quantitative
390 information.

391

392 4. Water-reuse regulations

393 Three main approaches regarding water-reuse regulations have been identified[14].

394 i. Based on limiting values that are defined for several parameters related to
395 reclaimed water. Health and/or environmental risks can be minimised by
396 meeting these values, which may be applicable at different points based on the
397 standards (e.g. at the reclaimed water delivery point or facility outlet). This
398 approach is followed by the EU members such as Italy, Spain, France, Cyprus,
399 Greece and Portugal [28] and requires intensive monitoring of water quality,
400 which can be highly challenging when analysing emerging pollutants [15,16].

401 ii. Based on wastewater treatment requirements and limiting values. This approach
402 has been reported in Title 22 of California's Code of Regulations and followed by
403 the EPA guidelines [39]. For each potential use, a specific approved and certified
404 wastewater treatment technique is required. For certain use categories, the
405 water quality criteria (limiting values) can also be applied.

406 iii. Based on implementing a risk management system for each reuse project. This
407 approach was adopted by the Australian guidelines [40] and WHO guidelines
408 [34], followed by the DEMOWARE manual [41]. An advantage of this approach is
409 the prior identification and management of risks more proactively, rather than
410 relying on post-treatment analysis and response when problems have already
411 arisen. The approach is also more flexible because it can be applied to various

412 scenarios. The main health and environmental hazardous events must first be
413 identified and assessed, and measures to prevent and control the risks must be
414 implemented, followed by the implementation of monitoring procedures to
415 ensure that risks are effectively reduced to an acceptably low level.

416

417 4.1. National water-reuse regulations in EU member states

418 Although Northern EU members such as Austria, Germany, Denmark, the Czech
419 Republic, the Netherlands, and Belgium do not present specific regulations regarding
420 water reuse[50], some member states from the south (Cyprus, France, Greece, Italy,
421 Spain, and Portugal) have established specific legislation to regulate water reuse in
422 centralised WWTPs (Table 3). Thus, these countries have standardised these practices
423 in their territories. However, amongst water-reuse regulations, large disparities occur in
424 the approach to be followed, the number of parameters to be analysed and their limiting
425 values, as well as the sampling points and sampling frequency [27]. This situation is often
426 related to the fact that the regulatory framework has not addressed water reuse
427 holistically (considering all factors that may affect water reuse such as water, energy,
428 food, climate, health, etc.), but it has been commonly managed separately [51].

429 The regulations in Cyprus, Greece, and Portugal were delivered by environmental
430 ministers, whereas health authorities collaborated with their elaboration in France, Italy
431 and Spain. This likely influenced the main purpose of each regulation and widened the
432 differences between them. For instance, the main concern in Cyprus is related to
433 environmental pollution from nitrates due to land irrigation; therefore, industrial or
434 urban reuse were not in the regulations[52]. However, Spanish and Italian regulations

435 require the approval of the public health authorities before obtaining the permission to
436 reuse water [53,54]. Spanish regulation permits the highest number of possible reuse
437 applications, including private garden irrigation, silviculture and aquaculture, varying
438 the stringency of the limiting values of pollutants according to the final use. For each
439 reclaimed water class, limits are provided for *E. coli*, intestinal nematodes, suspended
440 solids, turbidity; whereas for agricultural reuse, electrical conductivity (EC), sodium
441 adsorption ratio and twelve other metals are considered [53]. Additional parameters
442 such as *Legionella* spp. or nutrients may be required depending on the intended use and
443 related quality class.

444 In French regulations [55], limits are not imposed for heavy metals or agronomically
445 valued compounds. Standards are only defined and divided into four quality classes for
446 six quality parameters including *E. coli*, chemical oxygen demand (COD), total suspended
447 solids (TSS), faecal enterococci, sulphate-reducing bacteria, and F-specific
448 bacteriophages. Greek regulations [56] permit numerous reuse practices, defining three
449 quality categories, combined with the required treatment performance. Quality
450 parameters include *E. coli*, BOD₅, TSS, and turbidity. Additional requirements are set for
451 large WWTPs, including 19 heavy metals for WWTPs > 2,000 population equivalent (PE),
452 and other 40 organic compounds for WWTPs > 100,000 PE, and parameters of
453 agronomic relevance. In addition, Cyprus provides limiting values for five different reuse
454 classes, considering the WWTP size [52]. Italian regulations have established stringent
455 limiting values, of which approximately 20% are comparable to those required for
456 drinking water [57]. Furthermore, they must be met for all intended uses except for
457 industrial reuse. These stringent requirements aim to ensure human health and
458 environmental protection considering all possible uses but can hinder the economic

459 feasibility of water-reuse practices, especially in less advanced or extended applications
460 [32].

461 *E. coli* is the most popular indicator of pathogenic contamination and is used in all
462 analysed regulations. Moreover, the determination of helminth eggs is included in the
463 regulations in Spain, Cyprus, and Portugal. French regulations also include faecal
464 enterococci as a supplementary bacterial indicator. Notably, the limiting values differ by
465 up to one order of magnitude, varying from the strictest levels of 10 colony-forming unit
466 (CFU)·100 mL⁻¹ established by Italy and Greece to 100 CFU·100 mL⁻¹ permitted by Spain
467 for certain quality classes. Spain and Greece are characterised as having the strictest
468 monitoring protocols (Table 3), whereas in Italy, regional authorities demand this level
469 of stringency.

470 The Portuguese Regulation [58] follows the ISO standards 20760:2018 [59], 20426:2018
471 [45], and 16075:2020 [43] and includes risk management. It considers the definition of
472 quality classes according to the fit-for-purpose approach, providing water quality
473 standards based on the intended use [60] rather than defining common limits for all
474 purposes. This requires the development of risk assessment plans for each water-reuse
475 case. Unlike other national regulations, the Portuguese Regulation also provides
476 detailed guidelines to support risk assessment in water-reuse projects.

477

Table 3. Summary of relevant information of National Regulations on Water Reuse in some EU countries.

Country	Cyprus	France	Greece	Italy	Spain	Portugal
Standards reference	[52]	[55]	[56]	[54]	[53]	[58]
Issuing institution	Ministry of Agriculture, Natural resources and Environment Water development Department (Wastewater and reuse Division)	Ministry of Public Health Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Fisheries Ministry of Ecology, Energy and Sustainability	Ministry of Environment Energy and Climate Change	Ministry of Environment Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Public Health	Ministry of Environment Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Fisheries, Ministry of Health	Portuguese Environment Agency
Intended use	Urban areas irrigation, agriculture irrigation, golf course irrigation, aquifer recharge. Only from urban wastewater.	Urban areas irrigation, agriculture, golf course irrigation, green areas not accessible to the public	Urban areas irrigation and street cleaning, agriculture, industrial reuse, aquifer recharge, golf course irrigation, green areas not accessible to the public	Urban areas irrigation and street cleaning, agriculture, industrial reuse, golf course irrigation, green areas not accessible to the public	Urban areas irrigation and street cleaning, private gardens, agriculture, industrial reuse, aquifer recharge, golf course irrigation, green areas not accessible to the public, silviculture, environmental uses (e.g., wetlands, minimum stream flows)	Agriculture irrigation, urban uses (landscape, flushing, fire-fighting, street cleaning, recreational uses) or ecosystem support
Quality categories	5	4	3	1 (apart industrial reuse)	12	5
	Protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources					Technical Guide on wastewater reuse, to support the implementation of water reuse projects
Regulated parameters (microbial)	20 (2)	6 (4)	up to 80*	55 (2)	Up to 90* (3)	21 (2)
Monitoring frequency	1/15 days; pH: 3/week; 2/year; metals: Chlorides:	1/week 1/two weeks 1/month	Turbidity, <i>E. coli</i> , total coliforms: 7-1/week ; others: 24/year 12/year	Regional regulations	Microbial: 3/week - 1/month; TSS: 1/day - 1/week; others: 1/two weeks - 1/month	1/week – 1/2 weeks, continuous operational monitoring

	1/month; Helminth eggs: 4/year.		4/year			
Risk management	-	Risk analysis of treatment and distribution malfunctions	-	-	Guidelines on permitting procedures and technical support for risk assessment for health and environment	Guideline for risk assessment
Public	-	Information boards in green public spaces	-	-	-	Communication to public

479 **: Depending on the final use and specific project requirements*

480 4.2. Regulation 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse

481 The European Parliament and the Council recently approved Regulation 2020/741 on
482 *minimum requirements for water reuse* [61] to increase the amount of reclaimed water
483 used in the continent and solve the conflicts related to the lack of standardisation. This
484 regulation was established following the principles of previous guidelines, to overcome
485 their limitations and adapt water-reuse practices to the current socio-political scenario
486 of the Union. The EU Regulation establishes quality limits for certain pollutants as well
487 as the frequency of monitoring and treatment performance targets for reclaimed water
488 reuse in agriculture, depending on four different quality classes in a fit-for-purpose
489 approach. Water quality classes (Classes A–D) were defined in terms of pathogens, BOD,
490 TSS concentrations, and turbidity. Microbiological pollution is assessed by the *E. coli*
491 concentration in water (bacterial indicator), combined with the total coliphages
492 (alternatively, F-specific coliphages or somatic coliphages) and *Clostridium perfringens*
493 spores (or spore-forming sulphate-reducing bacteria), which act as virus and protozoa
494 indicators, respectively. The limiting values of these parameters varied according to the
495 quality class (Table 4). The limits of *Legionella* spp. and intestinal nematodes are also
496 indicated for certain reuse practices. Water-quality classification also depends on the
497 crop category to be irrigated and irrigation technique. Class D can only be applied to
498 non-food crops, Class C applies to food crops with above-ground edible parts and
499 irrigation using drip irrigation, and Class B can use other irrigation methods. The most
500 stringent is Class A which includes the irrigation of food crops consumed raw, which are
501 in direct contact with reclaimed water [61].

502 Monitoring requirements also depend on the reclaimed water-quality class, in addition
503 to the specific parameter analysed. *E. coli* monitoring varies from twice a month (Classes

504 C–D) to once a week (Classes A–B), whereas BOD and TSS should be analysed once a
505 week, and turbidity must be continuously monitored. Validation and routine monitoring
506 should be performed before a new reclamation facility is put into operation.

507 The new EU Regulation also introduces WRRMPs as a mandatory step for determining
508 the minimum requirements for specific pollutants in specific settings to reduce the risks
509 associated with public health and the environment to the maximum extent. The WRRMP
510 should identify and manage risks proactively to ensure that reclaimed water is safely
511 used and managed and poses no significant risks to the environment or human or animal
512 health. Thus, this regulation combines the first and third water-reuse approaches
513 defined in Section 4. The Water Reuse Risk Management Plan is based on the key risk
514 management principles as defined in Annex II of Regulation 2020/741 following: i) a
515 preparatory step (description of the entire reuse system and the parts involved); ii) a
516 system assessment and risk management step (identification of the potential hazards
517 and hazardous events for human health and the environment, the population involved,
518 and the exposure routes); iii) an operational monitoring step (monitoring specifications
519 for different matrices involved); and iv) an implementation step (governance,
520 management, and communication plans). Risk assessment can be performed using
521 qualitative or semi-quantitative risk assessments. Quantitative risk assessment should
522 be used when sufficient supporting data is available or in projects that pose a potentially
523 high risk to the environment or public health. Based on the risk assessment outcomes,
524 additional requirements regarding heavy metals, CECs, and/or ARG are required.

525

526 *4.2.1. Innovative aspects of EU Regulation 2020/741*

527 EU Regulation 2020/741 fills a legislative gap by defining the requirements and
528 conditions for water-reuse applications. For the first time, a legislation is available that
529 standardises technological and quality standards across the Union. Previously, only a
530 few member states addressed water reuse with specific regulations, which differed
531 significantly (as discussed in Section 4.1).

532 One of the most innovative aspects of this regulation is the inclusion of water-reuse risk
533 management plans among mandatory requirements. This emphasises the importance
534 of health and environmental protection, which must always be ensured. Thus, the
535 regulation follows the fit-for-purpose approach, instead of the fit-for-all method that
536 has been addressed by some EU members such as Italy. Accordingly, not only are quality
537 limits established, but crop quality and irrigation techniques must also comply. This fit-
538 for-purpose approach aims to facilitate the techno-economic feasibility of water-reuse
539 applications, which is supported by the fact that, compared to national legislation, the
540 EU Regulation selected a lower number of parameters to be monitored to accomplish
541 quality requirements (Table 4). However, it also provides EU members the flexibility to
542 include in their national laws limiting concentrations of other pollutants such as ARB,
543 antibiotics, microplastics, etc. These compounds have been scarcely considered in
544 previous legislation but are specifically considered in this EU Regulation and the updated
545 Directive concerning urban wastewater treatment (under revision) [62] because of the
546 growing concern they generate.

547

548

Table 4: Pollutant concentration limits in national and European Regulations

Regulation	Cyprus [52]	France [55]	Greece [56]	Italy [54]	Portugal [58]	Spain [53]	Regulation 2020/741* [61]
E. coli (n/100 mL)	5-10 ³	250-10 ⁵	5- 200	10	10-10 ⁴	0-10 ⁴	≤ 10 - 1000
BOD₅ (mg/L)	10-70	COD: 60	10-25	20	10-40		≤ 10 - 25
TSS (mg/L)	10-30	15	2-35	10	10-60	5-35	≤ 10 - 35
Turbidity (NTU)	-	-	2-no limit	-	≤ 5 – no limit	1-15	≤ 5 – no limit
Others	Helminth eggs, COD, pH, conductivity, Heavy metals and metalloids, Fat & oil, chlorides, nutrients	Faecal enterococci, Sulphate-reducing Bacteria, F-specific Bacteriophages	Total coliforms, pH, conductivity, Heavy metals and metalloids, chlorides, nutrients, TDS, SAR, bicarbonate, Toxic substances including priority substances	Salmonella sp., pH, conductivity, Heavy metals and metalloids, Fat & oil, chlorides, nutrients, SAR, Toxic substances including priority substances	Helminth eggs, Ammonia, Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Heavy metals, SAR, Salinity and Boron	Metals, EC, SAR.	Total coliphages (F-specific coliphages or somatic coliphages), Clostridium perfringens spores (or spore-forming sulphate reducing bacteria), Legionella spp.: <1 000 CFU/L; Intestinal nematodes: ≤1 egg/L

550 *Lowest limiting value for Class A; highest limiting value for Class D.

551

552 Other innovative aspects of this regulation compared to the previous regulations are as

553 follows: i) monitoring requirements are explicitly expressed and therefore normalised,

554 whereas in some national regulations, such as in Italy, they are provided by local

555 authorities; ii) reclamation facility operators are defined, shifting the conventional

556 paradigm of wastewater treatment to wastewater reuse; iii) the relevance of public

557 awareness regarding the benefits of water reuse has been highlighted, following the

558 recommendations of previous guidelines (refer to Section 3.1.3 for details); iv) the

559 promotion of fertigation, a practice that combines irrigation and nutrient recovery and
560 contradicts traditional wastewater treatment schemes where nutrients are removed
561 from water instead of being recovered [6]; and v) the proposal of financial incentives for
562 water reuse and further research into the topic.

563

564 *4.2.2. Gaps and limitations in the Regulation*

565 Although Regulation 2020/741 has harmonised water-reuse practices providing
566 standards and requirements, some aspects have not yet been thoroughly addressed: i)
567 for risk management, key elements are listed but not described; ii) the methodology for
568 risk assessment should at least be semi-quantitative, but no further information is
569 provided; iii) some examples of control measures are provided, but a method to
570 evaluate their contribution to risk minimisation is not well defined; and iv) the legislation
571 specifies that the reuse system description must consider all the integrated systems
572 from the wastewater source to its final use, including possible external contributions
573 such as dilution of treated wastewater with other sources, but the regulation does not
574 specify a technique to address these aspects. This creates a significant gap in some
575 areas, such as Italy, where many distribution systems are managed by irrigation
576 consortia that generally use surface water to irrigate crops whose quality is not
577 monitored or regulated; thus, they do not have the infrastructure to undertake these
578 tasks.

579 A detailed description of the method to assess microbiological risks related to water
580 quality is available. Nonetheless, indicators, such as *E. coli*, *Legionella* spp., and intestinal
581 nematodes, are not always monitored in WWTPs. In many cases, they are only analysed
582 in the effluent, being unable to know the total log removal of pathogens in the WWTP.

583 Thus, it can be hard to ensure, due to the lack of data regarding the occurrence, trends,
584 and treatment efficiencies in pathogen removal, that the treatment system could
585 accomplish with the legislation (in terms of total pathogen removal), which may
586 discourage the construction of new water reclamation facilities. Moreover, pathogen
587 determination is expensive and can be affected by many variables, outer contamination
588 of samples, and the inaccuracy of the equipment and measuring methodologies.
589 Consequently, they sometimes provide results with high uncertainty. In addition,
590 standard methods for their determination usually require excessively long times of
591 around 24–48 h, which would imply an extremely long response time when pathogen
592 proliferation occurs. Furthermore, some techniques for pathogen analysis are simply
593 based on the presence of pathogenic microorganisms in the sample, and do not
594 distinguish whether they are active or inactive. In cases where inactive biological
595 pollutants are present, a reduction in their concentration is not directly related to a
596 decrease in risk. All of these limitations in current detection techniques hinder in
597 attaining the legal limits and increase operating costs (primarily due to the requirement
598 of higher doses of disinfecting agents) without necessarily improving safety in the reuse
599 of water. Thus, more innovative monitoring technologies and techniques must be
600 developed. Monitoring programs should be supported by digital tools, including
601 innovative sensors to monitor microbiological contamination or early warning systems
602 (EWSs) to provide real-time signals and facilitate rapid interventions when possible
603 hazards are detected. However, the regulation only considers standard lab
604 measurements to verify the accomplishment of quality requirements, limiting the use
605 of digital tools to internal monitoring procedures.

606 In addition to the aforementioned limitations, information is lacking on a method to
607 manage risks from other pollutants, such as CECs, ARG, and metals [4]. Monitoring these
608 compounds would lead to technical issues and high costs of analysis. Some authors state
609 that reclaimed facilities, end-users and other stakeholders should share these costs [49],
610 but no information is provided regarding cost sharing in the regulation. No references
611 have been made to reducing pollutants at the source. This should be promoted in these
612 (or complementary) regulations because pollutant concentrations in wastewater
613 influents are one of the most relevant factors influencing the final water quality [63].
614 Another important aspect (not specified in the regulation) is the monitoring
615 requirements of soils and/or crops. No information is provided regarding the
616 parameters that should be monitored, frequencies, or sampling points. This is crucial for
617 assessing the environmental impacts of water-reuse practices and evaluating potential
618 health risks, particularly for toxic compounds that may accumulate in crops and humans.
619 According to the proposed regulation [61], determining the need for additional
620 requirements requires the operator to compare the outcomes of the risk assessment to
621 acceptable levels of risk or water quality. The Regulation 2020/741 provides no further
622 guidance, except for referring to other EU regulations under Task 4. Optimising these
623 regulations or other environmental and health criteria to minimise requirements for
624 reclaimed water facilities while ensuring the safe reuse of water is a complex task, even
625 for water risk-assessment experts. Some authors have stated their concerns that these
626 difficulties, combined with the associated costs of reuse, might unintentionally lead to
627 indirect reuse [64]. Hence, supporting (supra)national guidelines is necessary for
628 operators and regulators to efficiently prepare WRRMPs that protect human health and
629 the environment without excessively hindering the water-reuse process [64]. To

630 overcome these limitations, technical guidelines for the implementation of WRRMPs has
631 recently been launched [65,66]. The structure is divided into 11 key risk management
632 (KRM) elements grouped into four modules: I) preparation (KRMs 1–2); II) risk
633 assessment (KRMs 3–6); III) monitoring (KRMs 6 and 9); and IV) governance,
634 management, and communication (KRMs 7–11).

635 In the preparation phase (Module I), the objectives, influencing factors, boundaries, and
636 actors involved must be defined. The guideline suggests the quantitative information to
637 be collected and the factors to be considered [66]. This is a crucial step because it allows
638 the contextualisation of site-specific characteristics into larger regional, national, and
639 European frameworks. In the second module (risk assessment), the system functionality,
640 exposure routes, and exposed groups must be defined; moreover, hazards and
641 hazardous events must be identified. Relevant information can be obtained regarding
642 health and environmental risk assessments, as well as exposure assessments, targets,
643 and pathways. Guidelines are provided for both qualitative and quantitative risk
644 assessment approaches. Socio-economic impact assessments are also presented.
645 Module III encompasses operational monitoring and specifies the requirements,
646 recommendations, and practices for the monitoring of different matrices of water,
647 crops, and soils. Finally, in Module IV, information can be found on the governance,
648 management, and communication plans to support water-reuse planning and
649 implementation.

650

651 5. Overcoming the barriers to promote water reuse

652 The implementation of water-reuse practices is complex and is hindered by many factors
653 (as discussed in Section 2). Consequently, in addition to managing proficient reclamation
654 facilities and developing WRRMPs that ensure the safe use of reclaimed water, other
655 activities, methodologies, and tools are needed to overcome these obstacles.

656

657 5.1. Improvement of social awareness and involvement of stakeholders

658 The water-reuse practices to be implemented must be accepted by facility operators
659 and managers, authorities, users, consumers, and the civil population, who have to be
660 aware of water-reuse benefits and its possible risks and safety measures. This is a highly
661 relevant factor because a lack of trust in water-reuse management can completely
662 impede water-reuse development [31,32]. Thus, engaging stakeholders and the general
663 public in the planning and introduction of water-reuse systems is important, preferably
664 at an early stage. This can ensure transparency, trust, and acceptance while gathering
665 useful information from stakeholders, which helps to align approaches. In addition to
666 the common dissemination strategies, consultations, and awareness campaigns that
667 have already been suggested by the current guidelines (described in Section 3.1), novel
668 tools for dissemination are needed. In this context, serious games can help involve and
669 train stakeholders and the general public in more sustainable water management
670 approaches [67]. They can also help decision-makers analyse different political options
671 for the future. A serious game was developed under the *H2020-DWC project* to evaluate
672 and communicate the existing nexus between water reuse, carbon emissions, energy
673 consumption, and food production in an integrated peri-urban wastewater reuse system

674 [68]. In this 'game', the user can simulate different WWTP configurations to reach
675 different water quality classes, and select different irrigation techniques and crops,
676 according to the EU Regulation 2020/741 [61].

677 However, raising awareness of the benefits of water reuse must be complemented with
678 the awareness about water scarcity problems because the perception of these concepts
679 can significantly influence both 'willingness to use' and 'willingness to pay' for reclaimed
680 water to ensure water availability [29,69]. In Australia, owing to a serious water scarcity
681 period during 2007–2009, a substantial investment (ranging billions of dollars) was
682 made to build and implement reclaimed water facilities. However, after heavy rain
683 episodes associated with 'La Niña' in late 2010, these facilities were underused.
684 Similarly, in France, water reuse is restricted to certain regions because this country only
685 suffers from local and seasonal episodes of water scarcity [37], whereas Northern
686 European countries hardly adopt water-reuse practices, as previously explained.
687 Countries should not wait for serious scarcity events to develop political strategies based
688 on safe water reuse. Building new water reclamation facilities, as well as the training
689 and education of operators, technicians, managers and farmers, can take several years.
690 Thus, immediate action is necessary to prepare for water scarcity episodes in the next
691 decades and ensure safe water availability to all users, which is one of the sustainable
692 development goals (SDGs) of the United Nations.

693

694 5.2. Additional methodologies and tools

695 Additional methodologies and tools can complement health risk assessments to boost
696 water reuse by promoting this practice to decision-makers based on the social,
697 economic, and environmental benefits of water reuse. They can also be used by water

698 utilities to align their companies with the EU Taxonomy's objectives [70], increasing their
699 competitiveness and providing them with an improved public image for administrations
700 and the general public.

701

702 *5.2.1. Nutrient management plans*

703 In line with wastewater reuse for agriculture purposes, fertigation is a practice that
704 combines water irrigation with nutrient addition, thereby reducing the water and
705 nutrient needs of crops simultaneously. Consequently, fertigation can decrease (or even
706 eliminate) the use of synthetically produced nutrients that require approximately 10
707 kWh·kg-NH₄⁻¹ (in the case of nitrogen) and approximately 20.7 kWh·kg-PO₄⁻¹ (in the case
708 of phosphorus) [71]. In this context, Jiménez-Benítez et al. (2020) reported positive
709 economic and environmental balances when a scenario based on fertigation of
710 anaerobic membrane bioreactor effluents was considered, that is, a return of up to 376
711 k€·y⁻¹ and savings in CO₂ emissions of up to 898.9 tCO₂·y⁻¹ for mid-sized WWTPs. Thus,
712 fertigation could be of interest to stakeholders owing to these multiple benefits.
713 However, the conventional method to deal with nutrients in the wastewater treatment
714 sector mostly focuses on their removal to meet legal requirements (especially when the
715 plant emits their effluents to sensitive areas). This is an inefficient approach if
716 wastewater is reused because nutrient removal in treatment plans is commonly energy-
717 intensive and challenging for WWTP operators. However, excessive addition of nutrients
718 can lead to environmental and health issues, such as crop-related problems, nutrient
719 leaching, and runoff, which can result in groundwater pollution and/or eutrophication
720 of water bodies [7,72]. Hence, nutrient management plans (NMPs), that are planning to
721 be mandatory in the EU in the future, should be developed to regulate nutrient addition

722 to soil, thus ensuring their safe use. According to Seco et al. (2018) [27], NMPs should
723 contain the following elements: i) a water balance considering the effluents from
724 reclaimed facilities, returns to water bodies through distribution pipelines, irrigation
725 systems and fields, evapotranspiration, and crop requirements; ii) a nutrient balance
726 that considers their concentrations in reclaimed water, nutrient losses associated with
727 returns, variations in concentration due to evapotranspiration, crop nutrient
728 requirements, and mineral fertilisation; and iii) an economic balance that accounts for
729 different monetary flows within the reuse system, such as costs of purification,
730 pumping, fertilisers, irrigation water, and management plans. Thus, NMPs are aligned
731 with risk management plans and can complement them to increase reclaimed water
732 production by strengthening the support of general users and decision-makers.

733

734 *5.2.2. Assessment methodologies*

735 Standard assessment methodologies can help to quantify the benefits of water reuse
736 practices and analyse their risks. Thus, they can be powerful tools for raising the
737 awareness of decision-makers, stakeholders, and the general public [71,73] , so that
738 they can be combined with health risk management and NMPs. In this respect, life cycle
739 assessment (LCA) aims to quantify the environmental impacts of processes through the
740 entire production chain, can be useful in evaluating scenarios where irrigation or
741 fertigation using reclaimed water is considered and to quantitatively demonstrate their
742 benefits compared to conventional treatment schemes [74,75]. For instance, Foglia et
743 al. [76] evaluated water-reuse scenarios in the Peschiera Borromeo WWTP (Italy) using
744 an LCA. They observed lower impacts on climate change (-28%), fossil fuel depletion (-
745 31%), mineral resource depletion (-52%), and freshwater ecotoxicity (-35%) in a

746 treatment scenario based on anaerobic treatment coupled with ultrafiltration,
747 compared to a baseline scenario using a conventional activated sludge system coupled
748 with ultraviolet disinfection.

749 As a step beyond LCA assessment, the water-energy-food-climate (WEFC) or water-
750 energy-food-ecosystems (WEFE) nexus link water and energy consumption, carbon
751 emissions, environmental impacts, and food production in agriculture focusing on
752 synergies and trade-offs at the physical, digital, socio-economic, and governance levels.
753 It can be assessed through a systematic approach of design, scientific investigation, and
754 policy instruments and indicates a paradigm shift in wastewater management, from
755 simply considering the environmental impacts related to wastewater discharge to
756 assessing all the impacts (positive or negative) related to the processes with the ultimate
757 goal of carbon neutrality and long-term sustainability [51,71,73]. Thus, nexus
758 assessment is a novel approach that can be combined with risk management and NMPs
759 to ensure safe and sustainable water reuse, with the aim of ensuring water and food
760 availability in the subsequent decades.

761

762 [5.3. Digital tools related to water reuse](#)

763 Water and wastewater management have improved considerably (especially in the last
764 decade) owing to technological progress that has provided innovative sensors and tools
765 to support and implement monitoring and control systems, combined with tools to
766 treat, process, and analyse the data [77]. In addition to the tools used to increase
767 awareness, such as serious games (discussed in Section 5.1), digital tools can be used to
768 improve the performance of reclaimed water facilities in their daily activities, to achieve
769 a smart wastewater treatment sector [51,78]. Sensors can be used for treatment

770 optimisation and energy savings by facilitating rapid responses through real-time
771 monitoring. In contrast, EWSs can be used for monitoring, data analysis, and decision
772 support [79,80]. They can rapidly detect system malfunctions or anomalous event
773 occurrences, thus overcoming technical barriers related to delay in data acquisition from
774 grab samples due to the lag time between sampling, measuring, and data analysis.
775 Different reclamation schemes have also used EWSs for water quality monitoring and
776 rapid communication, such as the Médenine WWTP (Tunisia) [81]; or the Peschiera
777 Borromeo WWTP (Italy), where an EWS has been deployed within H2020-DWC project
778 for safe water reuse in agriculture. Data from sensors were used to forecast wastewater
779 quality using artificial neural networks to develop soft sensors and time-series
780 predictions, facilitating rapid response when a warning of non-compliance with reuse
781 standards is provided [82]. Affordable sensors have been commonly used to predict
782 trends in critical parameters that are not usually monitored or for which faulty signals
783 may be generated. Thus, EWSs can be easily integrated into existing monitoring
784 networks of WWTPs, supporting the digitisation of monitoring and control systems
785 without overloading analytical laboratories or installing expensive sensors.

786

787 Conclusions

788 The reuse of wastewater for irrigation or fertigation is currently far from its potential
789 use. Many factors hinder its development. Some are related to the feasibility of the
790 reclamation process and the potentially toxic compounds present in the reclaimed
791 water. In contrast, others are economic and socio-political, associated with a lack of trust
792 among stakeholders and the general public in water-reuse techniques and practices, the

793 unwillingness of politicians to invest in reclamation facilities, and others. The lack of
794 homogeneity in water-reuse regulations has been generally another relevant challenge.
795 The EU Regulation 2020/741 was recently approved to overcome these challenges and
796 standardise the legal requirements of reclaimed water to be considered fit for reuse. A
797 novel aspect of this regulation is the need to elaborate on WRRMPs in all reclamation
798 facilities to minimise health risks and protect the environment when reclaimed water is
799 used. In addition to ensuring safe water reuse, WRRMPs aim to transform people's
800 opinions by increasing their awareness of the benefits of reusing water and reducing
801 their biased opinions on the risks of using reclaimed water. To achieve these goals, the
802 gaps in existing guidelines and regulations, as well as the difficulties faced by water-
803 reuse professionals during the implementation of reclaimed water processes must be
804 identified. Some key aspects to be considered are the importance of guidelines for
805 developing efficient WRRMPs that ensure safe health and environmental protection as
806 well as the capital and operating costs related to modern reclaimed water facilities.
807 NMPs and other assessment methodologies, such as LCA and WEFC nexus, can be
808 combined with WRRMPs and contribute to the development of water-reuse practices.
809 Digital tools have also been found to improve the efficiency and applicability of water-
810 reuse technologies and increase public awareness. Most importantly, pollutant
811 reduction at source is a key factor to improve reclaimed water quality and can help
812 improve people's perception of wastewater reuse technology.

813

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